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Central California Health Foundation

TRANSPORTATION- LIMITED FOOD DESERTS AND HYPERTENSION: A CENSUS TRACT ANALYSIS IN CALIFORNIA

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INTRODUCTION

Uncontrolled hypertension contributes to cardiovascular disease, rising healthcare costs, and years of life lost, making it a major public health concern.^{1,2} In California, nearly 28% of adults report high blood pressure,³ disproportionately affecting structurally underserved communities.⁴ While personal risk factors are known, environmental drivers, like food deserts with limited transportation, remain understudied.

This study investigates the association between hypertension and transportation-limited food deserts across 7,743 California census tracts, accounting for socioeconomic and environmental variables like park access, walkability, and cumulative socioeconomic advantage.

METHODS

We conducted an ecological analysis using 2021 data from five sources: CDC PLACES (hypertension prevalence),⁵ USDA Food Access Research Atlas (food deserts),⁶ Healthy Places Index,⁷ ACS,⁸ and the EPA's Walkability Index.⁹ Our outcome variable was tract-level hypertension prevalence.

Figure 1. Infographic showing the link between food deserts and hypertension across geographic areas.

The main exposure was a binary classification of transportation-limited food deserts. Covariates included walkability, park access, rurality, and sociodemographics (age 55+, African American/Black %, cumulative socioeconomic advantage).

Data were cleaned in SPSS.¹⁰ We used stepwise multiple linear regression with collinearity diagnostics. Mapping was done using ArcGIS¹¹ to visualize hypertension and transportation-limited food deserts.

Variables	B	Std. Error	95% CI	P
(Constant)	27.23	0.126	26.98, 27.48	0
Transportation-Limited Food Deserts	1.96	0.123	1.72, 2.20	< 0.001
Cumulative socioeconomic advantage	-2.84	0.04	-2.92, -2.76	< 0.001
Age 55+	3.94	0.036	3.87, 4.01	< 0.001
African American/Black	1.05	0.031	.99, 1.10	< 0.001
Walkability	-0.37	0.037	-.44, -.29	< 0.001
Park access	-0.15	0.032	-.21, -.08	< 0.001
Rural	0.32	0.132	.06, .58	0.015

Table 1. Multiple Linear Regression Results Showing Associations Between Hypertension Prevalence and Environmental and Sociodemographic Factors Across California Census Tracts.

RESULTS

We analyzed 7,743 California census tracts to explore links between hypertension and environmental and sociodemographic factors. On average, 27% of adults had hypertension, and 6.3% of tracts were transportation-limited food deserts. Table 1 shows regression results assessing associations with food access, demographics, and built environment indicators.

- Regression Results:
 - Significant positive associations:
 - Transportation-Limited Food Deserts (B = 1.96, p < 0.001)
 - Age 55+, African American/Black %, rural tracts
 - Significant negative associations:
 - Walkability, park access, cumulative socioeconomic advantage

These findings show that structural inequities, specifically compounded food access and transportation barriers, elevate hypertension prevalence beyond traditional risk factors.

Figure 2. Hypertension prevalence (%) by census tract in California (CDC PLACES, 2021).

Figure 3. Transportation-limited food deserts by census tract in California (USDA FARA, 2019).

DISCUSSION

This study reinforces that environmental and social determinants significantly shape chronic disease patterns. Transportation-limited food deserts heighten hypertension risk, particularly in rural and racially marginalized communities. Walkable areas and green space access emerged as protective factors. Interventions must address compounded barriers, not just food availability, but also transit equity.

PUBLIC HEALTH SIGNIFICANCE

This study underscores how transportation-limited food deserts contribute to higher hypertension rates, especially in underserved and rural communities. Improving food access, transportation, and walkability can reduce chronic disease risk and support health equity in California.

FUTURE RESEARCH

Future work should use longitudinal data and expand to other regions. Incorporating individual-level factors like diet and stress, along with spatial analysis, can help design more targeted, equity-driven public health interventions.

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APPENDIX A

Hypertension Prevalence by Census Tract in California

Map displaying the percentage of adults diagnosed with hypertension, based on CDC PLACES 2021 data. Darker shades indicate higher prevalence. This visualization highlights geographic disparities across the state.

APPENDIX B

Transportation-Limited Food Deserts in California

Binary map identifying census tracts classified as food deserts with limited vehicle access. These areas are shaded to reflect compounded barriers to healthy food access, based on USDA definitions.